

Physico-chemical properties of soils of West Bengal mainly from non-deltaic region

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Soils from different locations of West Bengal from non-deltaic region were collected. The physico-chemical properties of soils like fine contents, moisture, pH, EC, exchangeable cations (K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) and less easily available cations were determined. The results were utilized to determine SAR (Sodium Absorption Ratio), Gapon constant K_G and K-status of soils. The parameters are important for the utilization and proper management of soils in agronomy.

Physico-chemical properties of soils are very much relevant to agricultural chemists for plant growth and soil management¹⁻³. Soil properties have been studied by different workers. It has been observed that the physico-chemical properties like cation-exchange capacities, organic matter contents, pH, electrical conductivity, K-status are of great importance for agricultural purposes. However, in spite of extensive agricultural activities, soils in different locations in West Bengal did not get adequate attention and are not properly utilised.

In course of our studies on the different engineering properties of soils of West Bengal, attempts were made to determine their physico-chemical properties. The engineering properties of soils from various parts of West Bengal were studied by the River Research Institute, West Bengal for construction purposes i.e. construction of roads, bridges, dams, buildings, pump houses etc. These considerations led us to collect surface soils and sub soils from different locations and attempts were made to determine physico-chemical properties of soils. The locations covered agricultural, non-agricultural and near agricultural fields.

The purpose of the study was : to understand whether a correlation can be made between the physico-chemical properties and engineering properties of soils and to ascertain the suitability of the sites for agricultural purposes and explore alternative sites for construction purposes.

Results and discussion

There are some micro-order diversities that bring out

different physico-graphic subdivisions of West Bengal comprising nineteen districts. The state have been divided into eight geographical regions⁴ and studies are limited to the regions 2-6 (Table 1) and the taxonomic classification is also given.

Geographical regions are :

2. Terrain region – Inceptisol and mollisol
3. Northern plains (Duars and Barind Tract) – Alfisol and entisol.
4. Rolling uplands and plateau scraps in the West – Inceptisol and alfisol.
5. Rarh – Alfisol and inceptisol.
6. Ganges delta [(a) Moriband Delta (Murshidabad, Nadia) – entisol ; (b) Mature Delta (Haora, Hooghly, parts of Bardhaman) – entisol and inceptisol, (Birbhum, Medinipur) – alfisol; (c) Active Delta {North and South 24-Parganas, Kolkata and Medinipur (East)} – entisol mainly, alfisol].

It is apparent that illite, kaolinite, smectite, vermiculite, chlorite are some of the minerals present in varying proportions^{5,6}. Exact clay mineralogy, though helpful for evolving better management practices for the soils and for better understanding of soil properties and mechanical strength of the soils could not be ascertained by us. The results of the physico-chemical measurements given in Tables 1 and 2, show that most of the samples contain sand (little in most cases), silt and clay in varying proportions. Fines content

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Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of soil in different location of West Bengal

Sample	Place, District	Geographical region	Soil description	Fines content ^a	Moisture content (%)	pH	EC dsm ⁻¹	Exch. Ca ²⁺ of dry soil [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. Mg ²⁺ of dry soil [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. Na ⁺ of dry soil [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. K ⁺ of dry soil [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	SAR [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹] ^{1/2}	K _G (mol kg ⁻¹) ^{1/2}
Lic-1	Lichupukuria, Darjeeling	2	Grey silt with organic matter	M	23.5	7.20	0.19	2.83	1.94	0.39	0.33	0.25	4.33
Isl-1	Islampur, Dinajpur (N)	3	Grey silty sand with trace clay	L	24.0	7.89	0.18	3.77	3.77	0.87	0.21	0.45	3.45
Rai-1	Raiganj, Dinajpur (S)	3	Grey loamy clay	H	25.0	7.28	0.31	8.85	2.01	0.91	0.29	0.39	2.83
Pan-1	Panchanandapur, Maldah	3	Dark grey silt with some sand	M	27.5	7.69	0.24	31.09	5.65	0.98	0.43	0.23	1.55
Dam-1	Dambera, Purulia	4	Brownish loamy clay	M	22.0	7.25	0.13	4.47	1.19	0.74	0.61	0.45	4.01
Bis-1	Bishnupur, Bankura	5	Brownish silty clay	H	28.5	7.42	0.16	3.58	0.67	0.61	0.18	0.42	4.61
Bak-1	Bakreswar, Birbhum	5	Brownish grey silty clay	H	14.5	7.53	0.21	17.43	3.29	1.04	0.64	0.32	2.07
Aus-1	Ausgram, Bardhaman	5-6	Yellowish brown silty clay	H	31.0	8.86	0.42	16.02	3.76	0.65	0.61	0.21	2.07
Bal-1	Balagarh, Hooghly	6	Silty clay	H	25.3	6.93	0.20	12.00	3.78	2.20	0.47	0.78	2.38
Kar-1	Karkaria, Nadia	6	Grey clayey sand	L	22.0	7.40	1.26	23.55	12.24	1.09	0.64	0.26	1.46
Jal-1	Jalangi, Murshidabad	6	Brownish silty clay	H	23.0	7.00	0.19	9.20	4.80	1.28	0.65	0.48	2.53
Kol-1	Kolaghat, Medinipur (E)	6	Grey silty sand	L	26.0	8.15	0.29	19.78	4.71	0.87	0.28	0.25	1.89
Dan-1	Danipur, Tamluk, Medinipur (E)	6	Silty clay	H	46.6	7.25	1.12	6.59	4.71	6.74	1.56	2.83	2.62
Amt-1	Amta, Haora	6	Grey silty clay	H	45.0	7.64	1.95	19.00	6.35	6.43	1.48	1.80	1.68
Geo-1	Geokhali, Medinipur (E)	6	Brownish grey silty clay	H	12.5	6.95	0.95	20.53	2.83	1.30	0.38	0.38	1.84
Kol-1	Kolkata	6	Grey sandy silt	M	48.0	8.40	0.31	24.50	6.67	1.00	0.62	0.25	1.67
Bas-1	Basirhat, 24-Prgs (N)	6	Silty clay	H	27.5	8.50	1.65	38.80	3.68	5.52	0.38	1.20	1.32
Boj-1	Bojerhat, 24-Prgs (S)	6	Sandy silt	L	21.5	7.94	0.40	35.80	7.63	1.45	0.71	0.31	1.40

^aFines content (in respect of particles finer than 60 micron); H = high (>80%), M = medium (40–80%), L = low (0–40%), N = Nil (0).

usually is from high (H) to medium (M). The moisture content of the soils ranges from 20–50% in general with exceptions. From Darjeeling to Raiganj, moisture contents are

relatively low. Moisture content (20–30%) and air (20–30%) can be regarded to be ideal for agricultural purposes.

Table 2. Amount of exchangeable ions at stress condition (HNO₃ extraction) (all concentration in respect of dry soil)

Sample Place, District	Geographical region	Soil description	Total K [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. K ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Non-Exch. K ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Total Na ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. Na ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Non-Exch. Na ⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Total Ca ²⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. Ca ²⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Non-Exch. Ca ²⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Total Mg ²⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Exch. Mg ²⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Non-Exch. Mg ²⁺ [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]
Rai-1	Raigang, U. Dinajpur (low lying)	3 Grey silty sand	0.36	0.20	0.16	1.09	0.87	0.22	3.50	2.52	0.98	1.50	0.73	0.77
Nag-1	Bhatol, U. Dinajpur (Nagar River)	3 Silty clay	2.56	0.36	2.20	1.48	0.61	0.87	10.00	3.60	6.40	6.00	1.00	5.00
Kar-1	Karru dam, Purulia	4 Loamy clay	1.89	0.60	1.29	3.69	3.22	0.47	9.50	4.00	5.50	5.50	1.73	3.77
Fut-1	Futiary dam, Purulia	4 Clayey sand	0.59	0.27	0.32	4.78	2.09	2.69	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hin-1	Hinglow dam, Birbhum	5 Silty clay	1.02	0.64	0.38	4.13	1.04	3.09	-	-	-	-	-	-
May-1	Mayurakshi canal, Birbhum	5 Silty clay	0.82	0.41	0.41	1.22	0.69	0.53	8.00	4.20	3.80	2.00	1.00	1.00
Sub-1	Submarekha, Bhasraghat, Medinipur (W)	5 Clayey silt	0.97	0.26	0.71	1.13	0.69	0.44	5.00	4.40	0.60	6.00	1.60	4.40
Hal-1	Haldi River, Haldia, Medinipur (E)	6 Silty clay	6.26	1.97	4.29	10.65	8.69	1.96	34.00	33.92	0.08	24.01	4.71	19.30
Shy-1	Shampur, Howrah	6 Silty clay	4.45	1.38	3.07	3.65	2.30	1.35	12.00	6.00	6.00	11.00	3.60	7.40
Ful-1	Fuleshar, Howrah	6 Silty clay	3.50	0.33	3.17	3.74	1.22	2.52	48.00	15.00	33.00	19.01	5.80	13.21
Dha-1	Dhamua, 24-Prgs (N)	6 Sandy silt	1.07	0.20	0.87	5.22	1.26	3.96	56.00	18.40	37.60	18.01	5.60	12.41
Tol-1	Tolly Nallah, Kolkata	6 Sandy silt	2.35	0.61	1.74	4.56	0.96	3.60	-	24.50	-	-	6.59	-

Due to dynamic nature of clay and humus content, the surface area of the soils are fairly high, a property related to cation-exchange capacities of soils and exchange of ions in soil solution. pH of the solutions in general can be regarded to be neutral to slightly alkaline, generally good for agricultural purposes.

EC values (of soil solutions), which measure the concentrations of exchangeable ions in solution, show low to medium values i.e. the cation exchange capacities are low to medium. In general, sandy soils with low clay and humus content have very low EC values. 1 : 1 type clays with humus content and Fe and Al oxides have relatively high EC values whereas 2 : 1 type clays like smectite, illite, vermiculite etc. with clay and humus content have high EC values. At neutral and slightly alkaline pH, EC reflects most of the pH dependent charges of colloidal particles as well as permanent charges² as the contributions due to H⁺ and OH⁻ towards EC are negligible.

Cation exchange capacity values of soils are fairly good if we compare the cation-exchange values with those reported by Sanyal and co-workers^{7,8} for the agricultural fields of Mondouri, Chinsurah, Bardhaman, Mohitnagar, Bolpur, Medinipur, Anandapur, Canning, Gayespur, Jhargram, Memari etc. The results indicate that these fields are good for agricultural purposes and can be used as such. Alternative sites should be explored for construction purposes.

As expected, exchangeable and total exchangeable Na⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions are greater than those of K⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions.

The sodium absorption ratio (SAR)

$$SAR = C_{Na^+} / [0.5(Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})]^{0.5} \quad (1)$$

are generally used to characterize the sodium content of soil solutions. SAR are found to be low indicating low sodium content of the soils except in places where there is silty clay like Balagarh (Bal-1), Danipur (Dan-1), Amta (Amt-1) and Basirhat (Bas-1) where SAR values are relatively high. Based on pH, EC and SAR values, the soils can be classified as normal for agriculture purposes in most cases^{1,2}.

K-Status of the soils :

In addition to N and P, K – plays an important stabilizing role influencing plant growth and stabilisation². K is present as relatively unavailable K (90–98% of total K), slowly available K (non-exchangeable 1–10% of total K), readily available K (exchangeable and soil solution, 1–2% of total K)².

In soil solutions, K⁺ ions are in equilibrium as follows

The exchangeable K and non-exchangeable K will thus be utilized by the plants^{7–11}.

For the determination of non-exchangeable K-status of soils, the following experiments are useful.

(1) Boiling of soil with 1 M HNO₃ (Pratt¹²) and determination of K – in the filtrate.

(2) Determination of step K and constant rate K (CR-K) by boiling soil repeatedly with HNO₃ and determining K after each step¹³.

(3) Determination of quantity (Q) and intensity (I) relationship of soils^{8,14,15}.

The step K and constant rate K or quantity (Q) and intensity (I) relationship were not studied by us. The determination of non-exchangeable K by the method of Pratt¹² is sufficient to suggest the amount of slowly available K under stress condition. However, the plants are not capable of utilising the total slowly available K as the plants are not supposed to exert the drastic conditions similar to that used by Pratt. Similarly, except for theoretical purposes, determination of step K and 'CR-K' should be avoided to prevent environmental pollution.

The exchangeable ions and non-exchangeable ion i.e. exchangeable under stress conditions are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Though the determination of only K is required but the release of K is always accompanied by the release of other non-exchangeable ions as given Table 2. The data will help us to find out % of total exchangeable, non-exchangeable and fixed ions in soils. Loss of K from soils are due to leaching, crop removal and luxury consumption of K.

Unless loss due to leaching is known with certainty, accurate guide for the application of potash fertilizer to soils for agricultural purposes may not be a reality even if the amount of exchangeable and non-exchangeable K is known. The K-intensity factor (I) or activity ratio AR^K of each solutions (ions in supernatant solutions in equilibrium with soils), potential buffering capacity and Gapon cation-exchange selectivity coefficient^{16,17} can be calculated as follows

$$AR^K = \frac{a_{K^+}}{\sqrt{a} (Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})} = \frac{c_{K^+}}{\sqrt{C} (Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})} \times \frac{\gamma_{K^+}}{\sqrt{\gamma} (Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})} \quad (2)$$

c is the molar concentration of the respective ion and γ is the activity coefficient. Activity coefficient can be calculated using the Davies equation¹⁸.

$$\log \gamma_i = \frac{0.509 Z_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + 0.2\mu \quad (3)$$

(Z_i = Valency of the ion)

μ is the ionic strength and is roughly equal to $\mu = 0.0127EC$ ¹⁹.

For the K- (Ca + Mg) interactions, the Gapon constant can be calculated from the relation²⁰

$$K_G = \frac{[\text{Exch. K}^+]}{[\text{Exch. Ca}^{2+} + \text{Exch. Mg}^{2+}]} \times \frac{\sqrt{a} (\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+})}{a_{K^+}} \quad (4)$$

K_G is not a true thermodynamic constant but can be assumed to have an indistinguishable thermodynamic value for ranges of monovalent ion-exchange phase loadings encountered in agricultural soil systems. Rearrangement of eq. (4) we have

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Exch. K}^+] &= [\text{Exch. Ca}^{2+} + \text{Exch. Mg}^{2+}] \cdot K_G \cdot AR^K \\ \text{or, } \frac{d[\text{Exch. K}^+]}{d(AR^K)} &= PBC^K \\ &= [\text{Exch. Ca}^{2+} + \text{Exch. Mg}^{2+}] \cdot K_G \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

The values of exchangeable K and other ions are known. Therefore PBC^K can be determined for the soil samples.

The greater the K_G the greater will be potential buffering capacity, PBC^K of the soil solution system. Excess Na^+ ions, addition of excess lime or excess K from excess potash fertilizers will disturb the equilibrium.

The Gapon exchange constants of the soils were found to be low indicating relatively low potassium buffering capacity i.e. low amount of exchangeable K in soils. PBC^K of soil is a measure of the amount of labile K in soil solution.

K-Status of the soils in the present experiment :

The exchangeable K and non-exchangeable K-values (Table 2) in most cases are good for agricultural purposes if we compare our results with those reported by others^{7,8}. K-availability of the soils under stress conditions is good for most of the soils. The non-exchangeable K-values may be taken into consideration for fertilizer (potash) recommendations for agricultural purposes.

The results may give some information regarding the

soil characteristics in different parts of the West Bengal. The physico-chemical properties of soils together with engineering properties should be examined to select sites for construction purposes which should not be at the expense of good agricultural fields unless urgently needed.

Experimental

The soil samples were collected from different locations of W.B. and at different depths by boring or by drilling with driving sampler. The soil samples, collected in containers, were sealed with wax to prevent moisture loss and sent to the laboratory for testing.

The nature of the soils and their grain size were analysed in way given in the literature²¹. Moisture content of the samples were determined in the usual way by heating. Soil pH and electrical conductivity [(soil) 1 : 5 (water)] of soils were determined pH-metrically and conductometrically. To determine exchange capacity of soils 10 g air dry soil was tilled well with 250 ml of 1 M of $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (pH = 7) solution for 3 h in an Erlenmeyer flask in a shaker, The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was stored in polyethylene bottles. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were estimated by titration with EDTA. Na^+ and K^+ were determined using a flame photometer²²⁻²⁴. Non-exchangeable K from soils was determined following the method of Pratt¹² by resorting to one time extraction by boiling with 1 N HNO_3 . In this method, soil : acid (1 : 10) suspension boiled gently for 10-15 mins over sand bath, the suspension is allowed to cool and filtered. K - extracted in this way minus the K - extracted by neutral 1 (N) NH_4OAc gave the non-exchangeable K of the soil. The other ions (Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) in the extracted solution were estimated and non-exchangeable ions were determined in the way given before.

Systronic digital pH-meter (± 0.01 pH), Systronic digital conductivity bridge and Systronic digital flame photometer were utilised for the respective measurements.

The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

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